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CORRUPTION AS A PUBLIC AND PRIVATE PHENOMENON AND A THREAT TO NATIONAL SECURITY

КОРУПЦІЯ ЯК ПУБЛІЧНО-ПРИВАТНЕ ЯВИЩЕ ТА ЗАГРОЗА НАЦІОНАЛЬНІЙ БЕЗПЕЦІ

The fact that national security must be ensured with the help of consistent determination of challenges to it was grounded. It was determined that the special place among these challenges belongs to corruption. It was defined that it is a public and private phenomenon, as it appears in all fields of social life, and a factor of improvement of the mechanisms of the state's influence in this field.

Key words: *corruption, national security, state, society.*

Обґрунтовано, що забезпечення національної безпеки повинно відбуватися за допомогою систменого визначення викликів ній. Визначено, що серед цих викликів особливе місце займає корупція. Установлено, що вона є публічно-приватним явищем, оскільки виникає у всіх сферах суспільної життєдіяльності, а також чинником удосконалення механізмів державного впливу в цій сфері.

Ключові слова: *корупція, національна безпека, держава, суспільство.*

Problem setting. The challenges and threats to national security of Ukraine have a complex nature. That is why they increase the importance and relevance of effective mechanisms of influence on them. National security of any country is often subjected to the influence of different factors, in particular the ones, which are considered exceptionally negative, noneconomic, etc.

Thus, it is significantly influenced by corruption, which in some fields of social life may be definitely considered as their attribute and constant component. Considering this, it is necessary to focus attention on the condition that timely definition of challenges and threats to national security of our country (especially lately) is critically important, because of their possible transformation into dangers.

Recent research and publications analysis. The issues of challenges and threats to national security (of the country, society and individuals), as well as the issues of their social and economic development are covered in the scientific works by O. Amosha, V. Bakumenko, S. Bielai, A. Diehtiar, S. Dombrovska, K. Dubych, O. Iliash, V. Kovrehin, O. Kriukov, N. Nyzhnyk, O. Novikova, O. Radchenko, H. Sytnyk, V. Sadkovyi, V. Skurativskyi and others.

Paper objective. Marking the scientific achievements of these scientists, it should be noted that there is the need in comprehensive description of corruption as a public phenomenon and a threat to national security, and of the peculiarities of the state policy in this field. Our paper objective is based on this.

Paper main body. The peculiarity of the existing situation in Ukraine is in the fact that at the moment, internal threats are considered as the main threats for the country's steady functioning and development. Speaking about the strategy of national security, it should be noted that the problems of this development are caused mostly by criminalization and 'shadowization' in the field of state control of economic and financial relations. The processes of criminalization in the indicated field should be considered as one of the main strategic threats to national security of Ukraine. Meanwhile, it is possible to single out such of its forms as corruption and raid, which today, according to Transparency International [5], have a negative dynamics of spreading and significant latency in the country. Significant is the fact that present-day corruption is not only a social and legal phenomenon, but also a public and private one, as it is peculiar to not only the state and its bodies, but also the society, while this threatens national security as a whole. After all, according to the state legislation [3; 4], the latter includes the interests of the state, society and individuals on the one hand, and is intended to coordinate them on the other hand.

Corruption as a negative social phenomenon is a present-day threat to national security, because it appears in both public and private areas of social life. This distribution is known from the times of the Roman Empire. In the second half of the 19th century, Rudolf von Jhering introduced the notion 'interest' [6] to differentiate between the private and public areas. Therefore, it is possible to note that corruption is a result of assertion of private interests, which are essen-

tially opposed to the public ones, or to the interests of the state and to the society. According to the Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine,” [4] these interests constitute national security and therefore need guarantees and protection.

The National Security Strategy of Ukraine approved by the Decree of the President of Ukraine [3] determines those factors, challenges and specific measures, which are focused on national security ensuring in the long term. The following ones should be emphasized:

- increase in the effectiveness of activities of state authorities;
- formation of single state system of prevention of crimes and other offences, including among other things monitoring and assessment of effectiveness of law-making and law-enforcement practices;
- development and implementation of special measures aimed at the reduction of the level of corrupt practices and criminalization of social relations.

It should be noted that p. 3.3. of the Strategy [same] contains provisions, according to which corruption is on the third place among the potentially dangerous threats to social and economic security of Ukraine. Essentially, the matter is in the fact that *corruption is the result of and the reason for ineffective system of state administration*. Corruption spreading, its strengthening in all areas of state administration happens simultaneously with functioning of weak, dysfunctional and *archaic model of public institutions*, as well as deprofessionalization and degradation of public service. Meanwhile, there is the fact that officials perform their duties in corporate and personal interests instead of public and national ones. It causes violation of rights, freedoms and lawful interests of citizens and economic entities.

It should be noted that the problem of assessment of the results of activities of state sector is quite difficult. The latest amendments to the country’s legislation did not solve this problem so far (see the Law of Ukraine “On National Security of Ukraine” [4]). Meanwhile, according to S. Dombrovska, Yu. Dreval and other experts [1; 2], it may be solved at the expense of scientifically balanced and legitimate determination of the indices of social and economic security, as well as complex use of the potential of analytical activity in their description.

The whole range of laws and regulations, particularly the National Security Strategy of Ukraine [3, Chapter 3], includes provisions, according to which the condition of economy and social area appropriately meet high requirements of social and economic security of present-day Ukraine, and shall be defined by certain qualitative criteria and parameters (the so-called “thresholds”). It should be noted that they are aimed at ensuring the following:

- reasonable conditions of life and personal development for the most part of the population;
- stable social and economic growth and situation;
- military and political stability of the society;

- territorial integrity of the country, its sovereignty;
- potential possibility to efficiently oppose the influence of internal and external threats, etc.

Therefore, the provision of national security of the state stipulates the formation of its effective social and economic policy, implementation of necessary institutional transformations and improvement of the state mechanisms, which are aimed at elimination of or tempering the influence of factors, which undermine the stability of national economy. All these things shall be implemented with the help of the adoption of the system of clearly determined measures, the implementation of which must be based on the complex of criteria, indicators or indices of social and economic security. The level of corruption in the state authorities must be among these indices.

Conclusions. In the process of formation of conceptual fundamentals of legal provision of social and economic security of Ukraine, certain mechanisms of state social and economic policy aimed at the prevention of negative challenges and threats to this security, corruption in particular, must be taken into account. The effectiveness of implementation of the measures in this field is determined based on the monitoring of factors, which assess challenges and threats to national security, as well as by way of the development of its criteria and parameters. On these grounds, we consider that a more detailed analysis of the peculiarities of implementation of monitoring of the level of corruption, which is a potential threat to national security of Ukraine, is a promising field of scientific researches.

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